

The Symbolism in the Book of Revelation

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Abstract

The Book of Revelation, the final book of the New Testament, has captivated readers and scholars for centuries due to its rich tapestry of symbolism. This paper aims to explore the intricate web of symbolism embedded within the text, shedding light on its profound and multifaceted meanings. Drawing upon extensive analysis of the book's literary, historical, and theological contexts, this study unveils the profound significance of the symbols employed by the author of Revelation.

Introduction

Apocalypse (*apokalypsis*) comes from the Greek *apo* (“from”) + *kalyptō* (“to hide/conceal”). Revelation is part of apocalyptic literature, as it corresponds well to its theological-literary markers. It includes a basic conviction that the present world is corrupted in a manner humanly incurable. Thus, a divine intervention that will cleanse the situation through a radical reversal of history is necessary which will bring the definitive victory of the good with the punishment and total destruction of evil forces. The book of Revelation, is a rich mine of spiritual wealth, much of which lies upon the surface, while even its deeper mysteries abundantly reward our careful search.¹ There are images that inspire awe, fear, and bewilderment. This makes the book of Revelation a truly unique book in the NT. The manner in which one approaches the interpretation of these symbols impacts the entire reading of John’s vision.

Content

The Revelation begins properly at chapter 1:9 and continues till chapter 22:5 and this forms the body of the book. The body is preceded by a title, an initial salutation to the seven Churches and a prologue. After the body, we have an epilogue and a

¹ S. A. Hunter, *Studies in the Book of Revelation*, 15.

final salutation to the recipients. John received two divine communications in two ecstasies (1:10; 4:2) which he unites into a single work in virtue of a command given to him (1:19).² In the first ecstasy, the prophet hears a voice which asks him to put into writing what he is about to see. In the second ecstasy a visual phenomenon accompanies the voice which invites him to come up to heaven.

The seven letters to the seven Churches in Asia Minor have the same components. They include a salutation, the identification of Christ, compliments are bestowed upon five of the Churches, but no word of praise for Sardis or Laodicea. We also see that rebukes are bestowed upon five of the Churches, but no reprimand for Smyrna or Philadelphia. There is also an exhortation to either repent or remain faithful. We also find a promise in every case for the one who is faithful.³ The main plot in Revelation is the fight between good and evil. The messages are conveyed by the author through archetypal imageries and symbolism.

Purpose

The Purpose of the Apocalypse, as indicated by its introductory words “*The Revelation*”, is the revealing or unveiling of mystery. The comprehensive design of the book is to unfold and interpret the divine purpose and method in human history, especially in relation to the redemptive process, by portraying in scenic outline the present and future course of the church of Christ through conflict to victory, for the vindication of God's righteousness in the final issue, and for the comfort and encouragement of tried and persecuted Christians in the midst of the pathway of life.⁴ The more immediate purpose was to strengthen the church in the strain of present distress, while the ultimate aim was the establishment of the moral order of the world. This purpose is presented by the portrayal of the world as an ideal battlefield full of opposing forces, with alternating scenes of triumph and danger. It reveals that the whole becomes a fervent and powerful appeal to the Christian life and character, as well as a clear call to new faith and courage.⁵

Methods of Interpretation

The book of Revelation can be interpreted in a variety of ways, ranging from the simple to the complex. The following are some of the categories:

² P. J. Sena, *The Apocalypse: Biblical Revelation Explained*, 19.

³ *Ibid*, 21.

⁴ F. Dusterdieck, *Critical and exegetical handbook to the Revelation of John*, 34.

⁵ S. A. Hunter, *Studies in the Book of Revelation*, 46.

Historicists

They interpret Revelation as presenting a sequence of events from the time of the apostle to the consummation of history.

Preterists (The Contemporary-Historical Interpretation)

This method presupposes that Revelation is wholly concerned with the circumstances of John's day. In its extreme form, it maintains that the author was wholly preoccupied with his own time.⁶

Futurists (End-Historical interpretation)

They interpret the visions primarily as events to take place in the future and the second coming of Christ.

Idealists (Non-Historical Interpretation)

They view Revelation as symbolic pictures of such timeless truths as the struggle between good and evil and the victory of the good. In this view, the book is concerned with ideas and principles.⁷

World- Historical Interpretation

Revelation is regarded as a detailed prophecy of identifiable historical events. It is shown as an inspired forecast of the whole reach of human history. The view presupposes a misunderstanding of biblical prophecy, which is taken to be prediction of future events of world history.⁸

Symbolism

The Book of Revelation uses complex symbolic language to convey spiritual truths. The use of symbols is intended to suggest the ineffable mystery which is spoken of. The symbols are also used to evoke the transcendence of the truths proposed.

Cosmic Symbolism

A quick survey indicates that the word κόσμος is used only three times in Revelation.⁹ The author uses real cosmic objects such as sky, sun, moon, sea. But

⁶ W.J. Harrington, *Revelation*, 16.

⁷ *Ibid*, 14.

⁸ *Ibid*, 15.

⁹ J.C. Coetzee, *Keys to God's revelation in the New Testament*, 32-33.

he often does not use them in their material sense but gives them a new meaning which expresses the divine transcendence. The cosmic “alterations” in Revelation are one of the more evident signs of the passage from the material sense to the symbolic sense. The threefold depiction of *heaven*, *earth* and *sea* in Revelation 10:6 stresses all spheres of life in this world, and thus everything of which God is creator and over which he is sovereign¹⁰

Heaven (οὐρανός)

There are instances in Revelation where οὐρανός is used within a normal frame. In such instances οὐρανός basically refers to the visible sky.¹¹ In some instances, οὐρανός is placed in a frame where it is understood as the dwelling place of God or the place of obedient worship to God. We see in Revelation 12:4, where John describes a third of the stars being swept from heaven (the sky) by the dragon’s tail. The stars here are understood figuratively by most commentators as references to the fallen angels.¹² In Revelation 4:1 and Revelation 19:11, *heaven* refers to the celestial dwelling place of God.

Earth (γῆ)

The second constituent part of the created universe seen in Revelation is the earth. Generally, John’s descriptions of the earth seem to fit into the ancient Jewish views of the cosmic order, as a physical place ‘here-below’, the place where rain, hail and stars fall when they come down from heaven.¹³ In Revelation, *earth* (γῆ) is attributed to the dwelling place of the inhabitants of the earth.¹⁴ The word γῆ in Revelation often has a sense that goes beyond its literal meaning of the physical world and has a qualitative reference. In contrast to *heaven*, *earth* is given a strong negative association, metaphorically referring to all that are unfaithful to God.

Sea (θάλασσα)

The *sea* (θάλασσα) is often used in Revelation within a context where it has a more or less literal reference. Sea refers to a body of water as part of creation. The sea in

¹⁰ G.R. Osborne, *Revelation*, 399.

¹¹ G.K. Beale, *The book of Revelation*, 636.

¹² G.R. Osborne, *Revelation*, 431.

¹³ *Ibid*, 251.

¹⁴ G.K. Beale, *The book of Revelation*, 290.

Revelation, is generally used as metaphor for something negative, such as the source of evil.¹⁵

Theriomorphic Symbolism

In the revelations, we see that *zōa* (“animals, living things”) is used twenty times, “beast” 38 times, lamb 29 times, horse 18 times, dragon 13 times; and also: lion, eagle, locust, frog, scorpion, serpent, dog, and bird. These terms have great metaphorical efficacy.¹⁶ Unlike fables, animals in Revelation are not protagonists to highlight a human characteristic. Rather, they show an element of reality that is between the human and divine worlds. The actions of the animals in Revelation always surpass that of humans while remaining under the control of God. They express a positive or negative force that acts in history until the eschatological conclusion.

Anthropological Symbolism

The author is interested in many aspects of human life, from the individual level (clothes, body parts, etc) to the collective (city life, cult elements, etc.). There are also surprising modes of dress. For example in 10:1 the angel is “wrapped in a cloud”; in 17:4, we see the great “harlot” clothed in purple and scarlet. The dress expresses the interior situation of the person. Due to the dress the people enter into a reciprocal relationship, for the others can see it, watch it, and confront it.¹⁷ On the collective level we have the two cities, Babylon and the New Jerusalem. Babylon symbolizes a city closed in on itself, closed to the transcendent. The heavenly Jerusalem symbolizes the Church. With these two opposed images come two united dimensions of symbolism in Revelation.

Color Symbolism

Colors have wide symbolic meaning. They range from “white” (16 times), “scarlet red” (4x), “green” (3x), “red” (2x), “black” (2x), and fiery red, hyacinth, and sulfur (once each). Each color has a specific meaning. The color *green* of the horses in the section of the fourth seal, indicates death, in the sense of frailty. We see that vegetation is green, but is destined to pass on. The color *red* evokes blood, indicates the cruelty that does not spare human life (cf. the second horse, 6:4) and also is the root of the demon (cf. the dragon, 12:3). The color *black* symbolizes a certain negativity, depending on the context: for example the third horse is black (6:5) and

¹⁵ S.J. Kistemaker, *Revelation*, 189.

¹⁶ G.K. Beale, *The book of Revelation*, 626.

¹⁷ D.E. Aune, *Revelation*, 439.

his negativity is tied to social injustice, indicated by the scene. *White* is clearly the color of the resurrection of Christ. In a generic way it refers to the divine reality. This color enters into play with the other categories of symbolism. For example, the “white horse” (6:2) indicating the messianic force typical of the resurrected Christ whereas the “white cloud,” that brings the Son of Man (14:14), indicating the transcendence of the resurrected Christ.

Arithmetic Symbolism

The context of the numbers is crucial for properly determining their symbolic meaning. In Revelation, the symbolic use of numbers becomes very complex, especially when we begin to consider “gematria”.¹⁸ Using numbers as symbols is very common in the Bible, especially in apocalyptic literature. The most significant numbers in Revelation are seven, four, three, twelve and, in some cases, we find the multiples of these numbers.¹⁹ *Seven* is the number of completeness. It expresses the totality and completeness of the work of God. *Four* is the number of the world, as the earth has four corners and the created world can be categorized into four divisions. *Three* seems to be a significant number without a consistent symbolic significance.²⁰ *Six*, which is 7 minus 1, symbolizes incompleteness, a lack of something. *Ten* reminds us of the 10 plagues in Egypt and the 10 commandments. Thus, it expresses completeness but with an undertone of purification. *Twelve* is the number of the people of God, squared for completeness and multiplied by a thousand to suggest vast numbers. So obviously important is the number twelve in the account of the New Jerusalem that the number can be found twelve times in Revelation 21:9-22:5.²¹

Understanding the Symbolism in the book of Revelation.

The dramatic composition of Revelation can be envisioned as a conic spiral, moving from the present to the eschatological future. Revelation’s language is not referential but polyvalent. It does not appeal to logic but to the emotions and so interpreters must acknowledge the ambiguity, openness, and indeterminacy of Revelation’s literary vision and symbolic narrative.²² As a mytho-poetic work, Revelation is not like a window to the world, but is more like an onion with layers

¹⁸ R. Summers, *Worthy is the Lamb*, 19-26.

¹⁹ J.P. Prévost, *How to Read the Apocalypse*, 29-41.

²⁰ R. Bauckham, *The Climax of Prophecy: Studies on the Book of Revelation*, 32.

²¹ *Ibid*, 36.

²² A. W. Wainwright, *Mysterious Apocalypse: Interpreting the Book of Revelation*, 227.

and layers of meaning.²³ It is worth observing that Revelation has some quite intricate features that are not obvious on the first hearing of the text. One can say that this intricacy of the Apocalypse becomes evident only on further and repeated study.²⁴ This intricacy suggests that the text was not designed to be read merely once, but that John's intention was for it to be read on a number of occasions so that its full impact could register in the minds of the audience.²⁵

To destroy these layers of meaning by reducing them through referential correlation, to only one definite meaning amounts to a serious misreading of the book. Rather than decoding either the images or symbols of Revelation into logical, inferential, propositional language; one needs to trace how an image or symbol works within the overall composition of Revelation's mythological symbolization.

Pragmatic Aspects: Interpreting Symbols in Revelation

While reading the book of Revelation, one needs to determine how the symbol functions in its context and try to grasp its significance. The correct interpretation of the symbolism found in the book of Revelation can be indeed a spiritual treasure in our lives. The following are some of the steps that can be of help as we read the book of Revelation.

1. Recognize the symbolic imagery associated with the description of people or beings, colors, numbers, institutions, places, and events.
2. Look for interpretations of those symbols within the vision.
3. Determine if the symbol stems from an allusion to the Old Testament.
4. Compare the symbol with other apocalyptic writings to determine if it is a common symbol with a relatively standard meaning.
5. Look for any possible connections between the symbol and the cultural-historical context.
6. Consult scholarly treatments of the symbol in commentaries and other works.
7. Remain humble in ones conclusions.

Conclusion

It has often been said that Revelation is one of the most debated books of the New Testament with expressions and categories that are strange and even disconcerting such as wars, bloodshed, beasts, dragons, various symbols and images.²⁶ It can be

²³ F. E. Schüssler, *Revelation: Vision of a Just World*, 19.

²⁴ J. Knight, *Revelation - Readings: A New Biblical Commentary*, 144.

²⁵ *Ibid*, 144.

²⁶ R. J. Faley, *Apocalypse Then and Now. A Companion to the Book of Revelation*, 183.

said to be one of the most encouraging books of the New Testament which presents a God-centered view of history and final redemption. It is apologetic in the sense that it defends itself against the problems of everyday faith. It can be said that the Church has found in Revelation comfort in her trials, and the assurance that truth, justice and virtue will triumph. The symbols that we find in Revelations are intended to reveal meaning rather than conceal it. Having seen the significance of the symbolism in the book of Revelation will enable us to have a much deeper understanding of the various events and thus interpret them in a way that they should be interpreted.

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